

"A Study on Credit Risk Management"

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ABSTRACT:

This Research Paper is based on the Study credit risk management in banking sector. This Project helps to understand what are the Financial Statements, Tools, Ratio's which shows the Current position of the Business or entity or a Company. The analysis of financial statements is a process of evaluating relationships between component parts of financial statements to obtain a better understanding of the firm's position and performance.

Credit Risk management underscores the fact that the survival of an organization depends heavily on its capabilities to anticipate and prepare for the change rather than just waiting for the change and react to it. The objective of Credit risk management is not to prohibit or prevent risk taking activity, but to ensure that the risks are consciously taken with full knowledge, purpose and clear understanding so that it can be measured and mitigated. It also prevents an institution from suffering unacceptable loss causing an institution to suffer or materially damage its competitive position. Functions of credit risk management should actually be bank specific dictated by the size and quality of balance sheet, complexity of functions, technical/ professional manpower and the status of place in that bank.

Keywords: Credit Risk Management, Bank, RBI, Organization

1. INTRODUCTION:

Identification:

The study first tries to understand which the risk associated with the banks are. Which determines the scope of performance of the banks? The need of study is that to create awareness about various credit risk related with banking. The study will highlight major area for banks risk management.

CREDIT RISK MANAGEMENT:

The Research Paper helps in understanding the clear meaning of credit Risk Management in State Bank of India. It explains about the credit risk scoring and Rating of the Bank. And also Study of comparative study of Credit Policy with that of its competitor helps in understanding the fair credit policy of the Bank and Credit Recovery management of the Banks and also its key competitors.

THE TERMS

- Credit is Money lent for a period of Time at a Cost (interest)
- Credit Risk is inability or unwillingness of customer or counter party to meet commitments → Default/ Willful default
- Losses due to fall in credit quality → real / perceived

Treatment of advances

- Major Categories:
 - Governments
 - PSEs (public Sector Enterprises)
 - Banks
 - Corporate
 - Retail
 - Claims against residential property
 - Claims against commercial real estate

Two Approaches

- Standardized Approach and
- Internal Ratings Based Approach (in future – to be notified by RBI later) –not to be covered now

➤ Standardised Approach

The institutionalized methodology is thoughtfully equivalent to the current accord, yet is more hazard touchy. The bank allots hazard to every one of its benefits and of accounting report positions and delivers an aggregate of hazard weighted resource esteems. A hazard weight of 100% implies that an introduction is remembered for the estimation of hazard weighted resources esteem, which converts into a capital charge equivalent to 9% of that esteem. Singular hazard weight at present relies upon the general class of borrower (i.e sovereign, banks or corporate). Under the new accord the hazard loads are to be refined by reference rating gave by an outside credit appraisal establishment, (for example, rating office) that fulfills exacting needs..

LIMITATIONS:

- The study is having time limitations of 2 months it was too short to learn risk management
- The study is based on secondary data available from monthly fact, websites and other books, as primary data was not accessible.
- The data of the project is based on quality. So there is no involvement of quantitative data
- The project is review based project so opinion of people may be biased

2. OBJECTIVES:

1. To study the various types of risk in the bank.
2. To study the tools and techniques to manage the risk for the banks.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This Research Paper is based on only secondary data. One of the most important users of Research Methodology is that it helps in identifying the risk of the banks and their various types. The required information or data and providing an information about how the risks are manage by the banks by using the tools of minimizing the risk. It also helps in collecting the vital information that is required for banking sector to assist them for the better decision making both day to day decisions and critical ones.

Research was carried out for managing the risk associated with the banks and tools to minimize the risk”.

5. FINDINGS:

First and the most important I learnt about risks in banking industry. Before this project I dint have much knowledge about Credit risk management. But now I have good knowledge about risk and Credit risk managing tools in banking sector.

I learnt about various Credit risk management tools which minimize the risk and future losses of the banks

I learnt which are the major risk impacts the performance, profit and efficiency of the banks

1. After the project it is find out bank is exposing following types of

- Marketing Risk
- Operation Risk
- Credit Risk

2. It is found that particular effective tool are used by banking industry for minimizing the risk

- For credit risk tool
- Review /renewal
- Risk rating model
- Risk based scientific pricing
- Portfolio management, loan mechanism.
- For market risk tools are
- Liquidity risk management
- Internal rate management
- Forex risk management
- Country risk management
- Nonfinancial risk management

3. Credit risk management process of SBI was studied on sample bases which shows that SBI uses following tools for minimizing the credit risk

- Risk Rating Model
- Exposure Ceilings
- Review/Renewal
- Loan Review Mechanism
- Portfolio Management
- Risk based scientific pricing

6.LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:-

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7. CONCLUSION:

Credit Risk the executives underscores the way that endurance of an association relies vigorously upon its capacities to foresee and plan for the change as opposed to simply sitting tight for the change and respond to it. The adequacy of hazard estimation in banks relies upon productive administration data framework computerization and systems administration of the branch exercises.

The viability of hazard estimation in banks relies upon proficient Management Information System and the hazard the board is rely upon which apparatus is utilized to limit it.every bank should utilize the appropriate instrument and strategy from different devices according to the hazard type with the goal that hazard will be oversee. The execution of hazard based examining would infer that more prominent accentuation is put on the interior evaluator's job for alleviating dangers. By concentrating on compelling danger the board, the inner evaluator would not just offer medicinal measures for current difficulty inclined regions, yet additionally envision issues to assume a functioning job in shielding the bank from chance risks.

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